

Logistics Performance Review: European Union and ASEAN Community

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Abstract:

This paper explores the logistics performance within and between ASEAN Community (AC) and the European Union (EU). The study makes comparison and inspection based on World Bank's Logistics Performance Indicators (LPI) of each economy and each collaboration. The finding shows big gap of logistics performance between economy in the collaboration. Where the EU is more advanced, and the gap is smaller, the AC is struggled with the improvement. The unbalanced level of performance within and between economies can be a big obstacle for future development as the global supply chain is unavoidable. The paper then discusses and suggests on the issues.

Keywords: logistics performance indicators; ASEAN Community (AC); European Union (EU)

JEL Classification: F42; F53; L98; O52; O53; O57

Introduction

This paper explores the logistics performance of selected economies in order to review the synchronized level of logistics system of the economic collaborations. Of interest is the newly developed ASEAN Community (AC) of the Association of South-East Asia Nations (ASEAN) and the European Union (EU). Where AC aims at strengthening the economies by integrating their resources and entering the world market as a single entity, the AC model is similar to the EU which has successfully developed its own mark and today has become a key player in global supply chain (European Commission 2014, Nugent 2017). Such collaboration allows that labour can be relocated freely, raw material can be sourced without any barrier, goods can be moved regardless of country border, *etc.* The supply chain will be redesigned to get into its optimal conditions. This open opportunity will result in higher competitiveness of the participating economies (OECD 2016, Hewitt 1994, Lambert and Cooper 2000).

This paper focuses on logistics performance of AC and EU because an active collaboration (investing or exchanging resources) requires that logistics systems may be levelled. Otherwise, it will result in delayed, unbalanced costs, or even insufficient quality of the deliveries (Houlihan 1985, Nagurney 2010). Therefore, the

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paper focuses on logistics performance of the EU and AC and to compare within and between the collaborations. The result shall be suggestive if a specific measure must be conducted.

1. The European Union and ASEAN community in brief

The following sections explore key economic characteristics and collaboration of the EU and the AC.

The European Union (EU) aims at creating a single standardized market, allowing free flow of goods, service, money and people. The sharing resource includes energy, knowledge and capital market. This creates stability, mobility and growth with a single currency and governing institutions. The European Union comprises of 28 European economies, covering an area of 4.4 million sq.km with a population over 510 million. The EU in 2016 generated a nominal GDP of USD16.5 trillion, contributing 22.2% of global GDP. However, there are big gaps between economies. Where Luxemburg are by far the wealthiest of EU, topped with GDP per capita (PPP) at USD 93,173, Belgium and Romania are as low as USD20,000 band (see Figure 1). The average GDP per capita of the EU is at USD 36,408 (Balcerowicz *et al.* 2013).

ASEAN Community (AC) is a cooperative initiative of South-East Asian countries. The aims are to integrate the economies into a single market and a single production base, allowing free flow of goods, services, investment, capital and skilled labour. Similar to EU, this collaboration would strengthen ASEAN economies to compete to the world (ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat 2008). ASEAN community comprises of 10 economies, covering an area of 4.4 million sq.km with a population of 629 million. ASEAN GDP is at 2,432 USD billion, contributing 3.3% to world. Here, there are also big gaps between economies. Singapore GDP per capita is as high as USD87, 100. Brunei GDP per capita is also high at USD79, 700. Cambodia is as low as USD3, 700 (Figure 1). The average GDP per capita of the AC is at USD25, 200 (ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat 2015, ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat 2016).

Figure 1. GDP per capita of EU and AC

Source: tradingeconomics.com

According to IMF report, ASEAN is rank 3rd in world's fastest growing economies. It has grown 66% since 2006 to 2015. Whereas EU has grown at the rate of 10% in the same period (International Monetary Fund 2016).

2. Logistics performance

Logistics is a key to economy competitiveness. Especially in today global supply chain, better logistics system allow and facilitate efficient flow of resources, goods and services. This applies to either a single economy or an economic community (Porter 1990, Monash *et al.* 1996).

Where single market and single production base are now applied in the AC and the EU, logistics system is then of interest. Each economy tries to improve their logistics performance both supporting systems, *e.g.*, customs, infrastructure, and operations, *e.g.*, logistics effectiveness and efficiency. Together with the advancement of modern management concepts and technologies, the terms "Industry 4.0" and "Logistics 4.0" are emerging. Cyber-physical systems and automation, digitalization and miniaturization are future trends. However, to become smart logistics, they must pass their minimum requirement. Here, the logistics performance must be at least good or levelled with their chain (Akinlar and Fraunhofer 2014, Lasi *et al.* 2014, Lee *et al.* 2015, Rübmann 2015)

Logistics performance indicators (LPI)

Logistics is important where globalization becomes localization and global supply chain becomes common. So-called "competitiveness", the country with better logistics performance tends to attract investment and trade and get more benefit in today borderless value chain. World Bank has issued a report on logistics performance of 160 economies, "Connecting to Compete - Trade Logistics in the Global Economy - The Logistics Performance Index and Its Indicators". Here, "Logistics Performance Indicators (LPI)" is used in this paper to inspect the logistics performance of EU and AC (Arvis *et al.* 2016). LPI constructs of 6 logistics areas, scored and based on global survey to reflect the logistics friendliness of each country. LPI is a result of qualitative assessment, aggregated and based on:

- customs: the efficiency of customs and border management clearance,
- infrastructure: the quality of trade and transport infrastructure,
- international shipments: the ease of arranging competitively priced shipments,
- logistics quality and competence: the competence and quality of logistics services,
- tracking and tracing: the ability to track and trace consignments,
- timeliness: the frequency with which shipments reach consignees within scheduled or expected delivery times.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 2 summarises LPI score of the EU and AC. It can be seen that the EU has overall higher LPI scores than the AC. This is understandable where EU's economic is more advanced. The average LPI of EU is at 3.61. Top 3 LPI score of EU belongs to Germany, Luxemburg and Sweden at 4.23, 4.22 and 4.20, respectively.

They are, in fact, world's top 3 performers. The 4th and 5th of EU, *i.e.*, Austria and Belgium, are also considerably world class, at 4.11 and 4.10. On the other hand, last 3 EU are Bulgaria, Romania and Cyprus at 2.81, 2.99 and 3.00, respectively. The standard deviation of LPI is at 0.43.

Comparing to those of AC, the average LPI is at 2.98. The best is Singapore at 4.14. Singapore is in fact world's 5th. Then to AC's 2nd and 3rd are Malaysia and Thailand at 3.43 and 3.26, respectively. Here, a big gap is present. Last 3 of AC are Cambodia, Myanmar and Laos at 2.80, 2.46 and 2.07, respectively. Laos is at world's 152th. The standard deviation of LPI of AC is at 0.56.

Figure 2. LPI score of EU and AC

Source: Arvis *et al.* 2016

In general, it is indicative that both EU and AC logistics system are quite unbalanced. The gap is big, especially the AC. This will be crucial in cases if the regional supply chain is required to be connected. The overall supply chain of the regions and their logistics performance can only be as strong as the weakest link.

In case of the further review, Singapore and Brunei economic are extremely strong for the case of the AC. It is too strong and creates a big gap of economics to the AC as a whole. Therefore, in this paper, Singapore and Brunei are then considered economic outliers of the AC. Also, Luxemburg is also considered an outlier to those EU.

Figure 3 investigates the performance trends of the EU and AC. Here, data dated back to 2012 and 2014 are used. Here, it can be seen that the performance of EU has improved. It jumps from 3.45 in 2012 to 3.55 in 2014

and to 3.59 in 2016. On the other hand, the AC are struggled with its improvement. Their logistics performance did improve from 2.88 in 2012 to 2.96 in 2014 but declined to 2.85 in 2016.

Figure 3. LPI: EU and AC – w/o 3 outliers – 2012, 2014 and 2016

Source: Arvis *et al.* 2016

Figure 4. LPI – 6 indicators: EU and AC – w/o 3 outliers

Source: Arvis *et al.* 2016

Figure 4 inspects in 6 logistics indicators of the EU and AC. Here, it can be seen that EU is advanced in logistics. The top score is from "Timeliness" at the average of 3.95. The rest of the LPI indicators also lies high at the average of 3.42 - 3.64. The EU's logistics are "world class". Many economies are world's best or even world's top 5. Germany, Netherland, Finland and UK are world's top 5 in terms of "Customs", scoring at 3.98 - 4.12. Germany, Netherland, Sweden and UK, also Luxemburg", are world's top 5 in terms of "Infrastructure". They score 4.21 - 4.44. Austria and Belgium also among top 10 of the world in many areas. However, some economies struggle with their capability. Bulgaria, Greece, Malta and Slovenia have "Customs" and "Infrastructure" scores at less than 3. Croatia and Romania also have "Infrastructure" of less than 3. Cyprus has "International shipments" at score of 2.80. In terms of "Logistics quality and competence", Cyprus, Greece and Malta score at less than 3. In terms of "Tracking and tracing", Bulgaria and Cyprus also score at less than 3.

On the other hand, the AC are struggle with not only to synchronize together but within their own development. "Timeliness" are found to be the most advance area at average score of 3.29. However, it scores much less than most of the EU. Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia and Vietnam have developed its capacity to reach a score of 3.5. However, Laos and Myanmar are as low as 2.68 and 2.85, respectively. "Customs"-wise, Indonesia, Philippines, Cambodia, Vietnam and Myanmar score 2.43 - 2.78. Laos scores at, world's 155th, 1.85. The average of the AC on "Customs" is at 2.65. "Infrastructure"-wise, the AC scores at the average of 2.61. Malaysia scores at 3.45 as the AC's best. However, Myanmar, Cambodia and Laos score as low as 1.75 - 2.36. "International shipments" is adequate for the AC. It scores at the average of 2.93. Laos and Myanmar are among the bottom at 2.18 - 2.23. In terms of "Logistics quality and competence" and "Tracking and tracing", the AC are quite weak. It scores at an average score of 2.77 and 2.82, respectively. Where Malaysia, Thailand and Indonesia top at over 3, Laos and Myanmar are among the bottom.

4. Cross mapping LPI with Gross Domestic Product per capita

It is obvious that EU has higher logistics performance than AC. However, it is also obvious that economics of EU is better than AC. The following section tries to handicap the logistics performance with GDP per capita in order to inspect the performance norms of these countries.

Figure 5. LPI vs GDP per capita: EU and AC – w/o 3 outliers

Source: Authors

Here, the trend lines (see Figure 5) show positive relationship between logistics performance and GDP per capita. This indicates that any country tends to have better logistics if the economy grows.

Focusing on the gradient of the linear trend lines, the relationship of logistics performance and GDP per capita are quite similar both EU and AC. From figure, it was clear that the EU are more progressed. However, the performance of AC can be better as the trend line of AC lies in higher vertical interception. This means that AC shows promising ratio of performance and GDP per capita. If the economies are leveraged, the AC will presumably perform better than the EU.

Conclusion

Focusing on overall logistics performance of the AC and the EU, the EU outperforms the AC, however, only with the advantage of current economics strengths. Average LPI score of the EU is at 3.61 with standard deviation of 0.43. The AC's average LPI score is at 2.98 with standard deviation 0.56. These deviations indicate the unbalanced logistics performance among countries in both collaborations. If logistics should facilitate economics activities, this big gap will affect on effectiveness and efficiency of the collaboration. The case is so crucial if the regional supply chain is targeted. It is also a big obstacle for future development, especially "Logistics 4.0" or such for the AC. If the countries or the community wish to enter the global supply chain, they shall focus on improvement to reach the required level of advancement. Otherwise, they will be left far behind.

The more advanced EU, on the other hand, cannot ignore these issues. They must also pay attention while trading with these underperformed economies. This is unavoidable today. Therefore, they must understand the nature of their partners' logistics system in order to get full competitive advantages. The collaboration within and across economies are needed.

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References

- [1] Akinlar, S., and Fraunhofer, I.M.L. 2014. Logistics 4.0 and challenges for the supply chain planning and IT. Available at: https://www.iis.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/iis/tr/Session%203_5_Logistics_Fraunhofer%20IML_Akinlar.pdf

- [2] Arvis, J.F., Saslavsky, D., Ojala, L., Shepherd, B., Busch, C., Raj, A., and Naula, T. 2016. *Connecting to Compete 2016 - Trade Logistics in the Global Economy: The Logistics Performance Index and Its Indicators*. World Bank, Washington, DC. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1596/24598>
- [3] Balcerowicz, L., Łaszka, A., Rzońca, A. and Kalina, L. 2013. *Economic growth in the European Union*. Lisbon Council, Available at: [https://lisboncouncil.net/growth/documents/LISBON_COUNCIL_Economic_Growth_in_the_EU%20\(1\).pdf](https://lisboncouncil.net/growth/documents/LISBON_COUNCIL_Economic_Growth_in_the_EU%20(1).pdf)
- [4] Hewitt, F. 1994. Supply chain redesign. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 5(2): 1-10.
- [5] Houlihan, J.B. 1985. International supply chain management. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Materials Management*, 15(1): 22-38. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb014601>
- [6] Lambert, D.M., and Cooper, M.C. 2000. Issues in supply chain management. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 29(1): 65-83. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501\(99\)00113-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501(99)00113-3)
- [7] Lasi, H., Fettke, P., Kemper, H.G., Feld, T., and Hoffmann, M. 2014. Industry 4.0 Business & Information. *Systems Engineering*, 6(4): 239-242. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11576-014-0424-4>
- [8] Lee, J., Bagheri, B., and Kao, H.A. 2015. A cyber-physical systems architecture for industry 4.0-based manufacturing systems. *Manufacturing Letters*, 3: 18-23. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mfglet.2014.12.001>
- [9] Morash, E.A., Droge, C.L., and Vickery, S.K. 1996. Strategic logistics capabilities for competitive advantage and firm success. *Journal of business Logistics*, 17(1): 1-10.
- [10] Nagurney, A. 2010. Optimal supply chain network design and redesign at minimal total cost and with demand satisfaction. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 128(1): 200-208. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.07.020>
- [11] Nugent, N. 2017. *The government and politics of the European Union*. Macmillan Education UK, ISBN-10: 1137454091, ISBN-13: 9781137454096, 512 pp.
- [12] Porter, M.E. 1990. The competitive advantage of nations. *Harvard Business Review*, 68(2): 73-93.
- [13] Rübmann, M., Lorenz, M., Gerbert, P., Waldner, M., Justus, J., Engel, P., and Harnisch, M. 2015. *Industry 4.0: The future of productivity and growth in manufacturing industries*. Boston Consulting Group. Available at: <https://www.zvw.de/media.media.72e472fb-1698-4a15-8858-344351c8902f.original.pdf>
- *** ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat. 2008. *ASEAN Economic Community Blueprint*. Association of Southeast Asian Nations.
- *** ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat. 2015. *ASEAN Economic Community - Chartbook 2016*. Association of Southeast Asian Nations.
- *** ASEAN and ASEAN Secretariat. 2016. *ASEAN Statistical Leaflet: Selected Key Indicators 2016*. Association of Southeast Asian Nations.
- *** European Commission. 2014. *The European Union Explained: How the EU Works*. European Commission.
- *** International Monetary Fund. 2016. *World Economic Outlook Database*.
- *** OECD. 2016. *OECD Economic Surveys European Union*.